

STUDY OF SPEECH CULTURE PROBLEMS IN UZBEK LINGUISTICS

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Annotation. *This article deals with the problems of speech in Modern linguistics. It provides information with study of speech culture problems in Uzbek linguistics.*

Key words: *speech, culture, linguistics, oral speech, written speech.*

It is known that "from the point of view of internal construction, language is a complex system consisting of a certain number of closely related language units and the rules for using these units." The well-known linguists H. Nematov and R. Rasulov distinguish the stages of language development and speech process in the style of "language-norm-speech" and note that "language is not given by direct observation. It exists in the minds of the members of the society and is considered as a set of ideas about the units and their mutual relations, which are ready, common, mandatory for all of them, and serve to form and express the opinion. Language, as a component of national values, spirituality, and even ideology, is not only a tool for communication between people, but also a tool for their education. Respect for the mother tongue is love for the Motherland. Honoring the mother tongue is honoring Uzbekistan, the motherland of that language. Attitude towards the mother tongue is an important tool for educating members of society. Attitude to language is a component of universal human culture. The mother tongue is the pride of the country. The culture, spirituality, intellectual level of the nation is clearly seen in relation to the mother tongue [1].

The Uzbek language, as the national wealth of the Uzbek people, has been honored, honored and polished by our ancestors since ancient times. The relationship of Mir Alisher Navoi, the founder of the Uzbek literary language, to our native language, the fact that he proved the possibilities of this language as an extremely rich, beautiful, unique language with his royal works, the purity, prestige, influence of our native language, as the pride of our nation, they fought for a high culture of speech and deserve all praise and honor [2].

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Language and speech culture are an integral part of society's life, because the mother tongue as an important means of education directs people to great goals, inspires them, and encourages them to live with noble dreams. The power of words and the fact that language is a sharp weapon can be clearly felt in the works of Alisher Navoi. From history until now, the attitude towards the mother tongue has been different. But the most important achievement is that the Uzbek language, as the most beautiful language with its deep roots, still maintains its wide potential as a national literary heritage with its rich lexicon, means of expression, colorful grammatical structure. Every child of the nation is responsible for revealing, developing and enriching its unique opportunities, and no one should be indifferent to its development. Uzbek language as the national literary language of the Uzbek people, raising its prestige, showing off its high spirituality and culture, and being proud of our achievements. Since it is the main tool to show our identity, it always requires care, attention, and maintenance. Maintaining the literary language and increasing its status is determined by strict adherence to its laws, i.e. the norms of the literary language. Attention to the Uzbek literary language is to ensure its status as a state language, to increase its role in social-political, spiritual-cultural, economic life, education and training, office work, publishing, high culture use in mass media, It is closely related to objectively evaluating the changes in z wealth and grammatical construction, taking certain measures when necessary, and making conscious interventions for language development [3].

Attitude towards the Uzbek language was not smooth during the former union. A one-sided approach to nations and their national values,

historical, national, religious heritage, including national languages, from the point of view of the ruling ideology, has led to discrimination of many nations and their languages. The extremely low attention to the Uzbek language greatly damaged its position in business, education, publishing, mass media, and even as a colloquial language. As a result, the wide possibilities of the Uzbek language were limited, the language of the mass media began to become more and more official, the language of translation, it became impossible to carry out a live conversation without Russian words. The lovers of our nation - writers, poets, journalists, scientists, teachers realized that the Uzbek literary language is in need of care and maintenance. At first, it started with certain passions, and then the bold steps taken with good intentions, such as raising the legal status of the Uzbek language, which is considered the nation's pride, wealth, and prestige, were taken by our people, most importantly. , our head of state supported [4].

It was not just an official name, but an example of respect for the pride of our nation, a symbol of spirituality. During the period of independence, the position of the Uzbek language increased tremendously: the state language began to be used in practice in social-political, economic, cultural-educational and all other aspects. The efforts of intellectuals, writers, poets, expert scientists, especially journalists have intensified to reveal the rich, beautiful and unique possibilities of the Uzbek language based on the spirit of independence, creativity, and national pride. In the first years of independence, a specific struggle for the prestige of the Uzbek language began. In the press, through radio and television, various opinions were expressed about the uniqueness of the Uzbek literary language, the use of words, the use of grammatical forms, and the creation of new words and terms. Among them, special attention was paid to the language of the press. This is not for nothing. Because the press is the herald of the nation, a mirror of spirituality, and an important means of education. The press is important for revealing the possibilities of the Uzbek literary language as a means of propaganda, campaigning, education, influencing, determining the level of its development, showing the laws and regulations

of the literary language, literacy, speech culture. The press plays a huge role in monitoring, analyzing, evaluating the process taking place in the Uzbek literary language, drawing appropriate conclusions, taking care of it, correcting wrong situations, and taking care of it. The Uzbek literary language has strict rules, i.e. literary norms. Strict adherence to the norms of the literary language is equal to showing respect to the mother tongue, the Uzbek people who are considered to be its owners, and our Motherland. In particular, compliance with the literary norm imposes a great responsibility on press officers, journalists and intellectuals. It is known that the role of language as a communication tool in society constitutes its communicative function. Expressing and influencing language is its expressive function. The expressive task includes the informative task of expressing a certain message and conveying it to the listener, and the emotive task of expressing emotions. At the same time, language is a means of inter-ethnic communication, a tool for preserving and passing on experience and knowledge to generations, and these processes are the accumulative function of language [5].

This function of language is also known as its epistemological (cognitive process) function. Therefore, language as a communication tool of society is a socio-historical, cultural and logical system consisting of speech sounds, words formed from their interconnection, grammatical tools and rules for their appropriate use, a sign of spirituality. The relationship between language and speech is also known from the following. Language is organized on the basis of speech and is realized through speech. Language is both the basis and the product of speech at the same time. Language provides material for communication, speech is the formation of ideas from this material. The survival, existence and development of the language is through speech. For example, I am speaking using the Uzbek language in my speech, so this is the existence of the Uzbek language, its existence. Therefore, every specific form of language is a real speech, a speech activity. Language is a treasury of linguistic (linguistic) units and rules in human memory. Speech is the active movement of these units based on certain

rules, performing a certain social task, that is, speech is a process, a practice. Both language and thought are social phenomena. Language and speech, which have a social character, are realized through each other, that is, language is manifested through speech, and speech is manifested through language. Language and speech are interrelated, related to each other, one

cannot exist without the other, but they are different social phenomena. Language is abstract, and speech is concrete, that is, we hear, acoustically perceive and see speech (in text). The speech is always clear and takes place in a certain place (place) and at a certain time. Speech requires the presence of a speaker, a listener, and an object - the object of thought.

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